

Detection, identification and surveillance of *Xylella fastidiosa* on vectors in France

Curty A*, Legendre B, Reynaud P, Poliakoff F, Olivier V

*French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety, Plant Health Laboratory (ANSES), Angers (FR)

The present work was presented in the framework of the Joint Annual Meeting of the EU Horizon 2020 Projects POnTE 'Pest Organisms Threatening Europe' (GA 635646) and XF-ACTORS 'Xylella fastidiosa Active Containment Through a multidisciplinary-Oriented Research Strategy' (GA 727987).

Abstract: *Xylella fastidiosa* was identified in natural conditions in France in 2015, first in Corsica Island, then in Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur administrative region (French Riviera). Forty-nine host plants have been identified nowadays, infected by *X. fastidiosa* subsp *multiplex*.

In France, the detection protocol on vectors is based on the real-time PCR Harper et al. (2010) after a high-throughput DNA extraction based on the QuickPick™ Plant DNA kit used with a KingFisher™ robot. This method was evaluated in 2016–2019 mainly on *Philaenus spumarius*, the most effective vector based on POnTE studies from CNR. This protocol showed excellent performance criteria on individuals and groups of insects, on spiked macerates of insects from healthy areas and on naturally infected insects from outbreaks areas.

Strain identification was performed using MLST scheme (www.pubmlst.org) with the PCR Yuan et al. (2010) (modified EPP0, 2019) for amplifying sequences of 7 housekeeping genes. A protocol with addition of BSA into the PCR reaction mixture has been validated, showing improved performance in terms of sensitivity and success for strain typing. The centralisation of surveillance data at Anses enabled the production of zonal maps of the distribution of strains according to host species. They have been compared to compilation of results of detection and strain identification on insects *Philaenus spumarius* from Corsica and French Riviera regions. A good correlation between both maps has been observed in the same area. This work highlights the complementarity of the approaches on plants and insects in the framework of the epidemiological survey of the disease in a context of high risk for Europe.

Transmission characteristics of *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *pauca* (ST53) by *Philaenus spumarius* and *Cicadella viridis*

Bodino N*, Cavalieri V, Dongiovanni C, Altamura G, Saladini MA, Saponari M, Bosco D

*Istituto per la Protezione Sostenibile delle Piante (CNR), Torino (IT)

The present work was presented in the framework of the Joint Annual Meeting of the EU Horizon 2020 Projects POnTE 'Pest Organisms Threatening Europe' (GA 635646) and XF-ACTORS 'Xylella fastidiosa Active Containment Through a multidisciplinary-Oriented Research Strategy' (GA 727987).

Abstract: For insect-borne plant pathogens, transmission biology is of major importance in outlining the disease epidemiology. The characteristics of acquisition, persistence and transmission of *X. fastidiosa* ST53 by the spittlebug *Philaenus spumarius*, the main vector in Apulia, are not yet described; similarly, transmission competence of the potential vector *Cicadella viridis*, the most common sharpshooter in Europe, is unknown. In this perspective, two sets of experiments were performed in 2017 and 2018 to study: i) the kinetics of bacterial multiplication and persistence in *P. spumarius* and *C. viridis*; ii) the influence of temperature, season and age of *P. spumarius* adults on simulated epidemic progression on olive plants under indoor and outdoor conditions.

For the kinetics experiments, following the acquisition, insects were serially transferred in groups of five to olive or periwinkle test plants. In simulated epidemic progression experiments, after the acquisition, groups of insects were isolated in cages with 16 olive seedlings for different inoculation periods. Acquisition and transmission rates were assessed by testing individual insects after inoculation and by testing recipient plants 6

and 10 months post-inoculation. Furthermore, acquisition and transmission of *X. fastidiosa* ST53 by *C. viridis* were tested through an *in vitro* acquisition system. Overall, about 900 insects and 170 plants were tested in kinetics experiments, while about 800 spittlebugs and 1,500 plants were studied in simulated epidemic progression experiments.

Preliminary results for *P. spumarius* indicate: a) a higher acquisition efficiency in September than July; b) a lower acquisition efficiency from periwinkle compared with olive as source plants, but higher transmission efficiency to periwinkle compared with olive as recipient plants. *Cicadella viridis* was able to acquire and transmit *X. fastidiosa* following acquisition on artificial diet or periwinkle, although with low efficiency.

Flight behaviour of *Philaenus spumarius*, the main vector of *Xylella fastidiosa*

Lago C*, Garzo E, Moreno A, Martí-Campoy A, Rodríguez-Ballester F, Ferreres A

**Instituto de Ciencias Agrarias (ICA), Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), Madrid (ES)*

The present work was presented in the framework of the Joint Annual Meeting of the EU Horizon 2020 Projects POnte 'Pest Organisms Threatening Europe' (GA 635646) and XF-ACTORS 'Xylella fastidiosa Active Containment Through a multidisciplinary-Oriented Research Strategy' (GA 727987).

Abstract: *Xylella fastidiosa* jeopardises key crops in Europe. *Philaenus spumarius* was identified as the predominant vector involved in the spread of *X. fastidiosa* in southern Italy. This meadow spittlebug is also distributed in other regions, including Spain. Understanding vector dispersal ability is essential to predict the spread of *X. fastidiosa*. This insect species was reported to travel as much as 100 m within 24 hours in the field (1). However, both *P. spumarius* and *Neophilaenus lineatus*, another potential vector, can vertically displace up to the planetary boundary layer so they may passively travel long distances by laminar air currents (2). Our goal was to study the movement of *P. spumarius* under laboratory conditions using a modified commercial flight mill. Field studies on vector movement using vertical sticky traps; directional malaise traps and capture-mark-recapture techniques are underway. Different biotic and abiotic factors affecting the flight behaviour of *P. spumarius* are being studied: gender, adult age, temperature, light, barometric pressure, seasonality, geographic origin and rearing conditions among other factors. The individuals were tested using flight mills to estimate the number of flights, flight duration and number of turns (distance). The number and duration of turns were recorded using two different procedures: 1. Ethovision XT (Noldus), placing a video camera above the flight mill; 2. Mill_recorder, a computer-based device programmed to register the number and duration of each turn. Our data available to date show that *P. spumarius* is able to fly a distance of at least 1.99 km in 1 h 40 min in a single flight, which is much higher than was previously thought. Furthermore, our preliminary results show that there are differences in the flight potential between males and females and between young and old adults. This knowledge on the flight potential of *P. spumarius* will be critical to improve management actions against the vector and the spread of *X. fastidiosa* in Europe.

Host plant affiliation of xylem-feeders in central Europe

Markheiser A*, Maixner M

Julius Kühn-Institut (JKI), Quedlinburg (DE)

The present work was presented in the framework of the Joint Annual Meeting of the EU Horizon 2020 Projects POnte 'Pest Organisms Threatening Europe' (GA 635646) and XF-ACTORS 'Xylella fastidiosa Active Containment Through a multidisciplinary-Oriented Research Strategy' (GA 727987).

Abstract: Provoked by the first notification of *Xylella fastidiosa* in Europe, several countries aimed to acquire data on the presence of already confirmed as well as potential vector species of the bacterium present in Europe.

In Germany, vector surveys were carried out predominantly on plant species which are economically important in central Europe and known to be highly endangered by *X.*